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ABSTRACT

So, the article contains information about what soil degradation is and types of soil degradation like water erosion and wind erosion. The article presents solutions to the soil degradation problem of Karakalpakstan. Also, chemical aspects, opinion of the international community, ongoing practical actions were considered and conclusions were given.

To the article "The main causes of soil degradation in Karakalpakstan"

REVIEW

The major types of land degradation in Uzbekistan are secondary salinization, soil erosion and desertification. Due to the arid climate, agricultural production in most of the country is possible only with irrigation. The main causes of soil degradation and, consequently, the main threats to its ecological functions are erosion, organic matter decline, loss of biodiversity, compaction, sealing, point-source and diffused contamination, pollution, and salinization. Soil degradation is the physical, chemical and biological decline in soil quality.

So, the article contains information about what soil degradation is and types of soil degradation like water erosion and wind erosion. The article presents solutions to the soil degradation problem of Karakalpakstan. Also, chemical aspects, opinion of the international community, ongoing practical actions were considered and conclusions were given.